

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Banana Peel and Potato as a Biodegradable Plastic

Fatima Ahmed Al-Qadri^{1*}, Fatima A S Al-Yusufy², Jawaher Al-Qahtan¹, Ashwaq Al-Hilali¹, Amnah Bawazir¹, Sarah Salem Al-Sayari¹, Sarah Suleiman Al-Sayari¹, Mona Al-Nahdi¹, Bakhita Alkorbi¹

¹ Sharora Science and Art faculty, Empty Quarter research unit, Najran University, Shoroura, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

² Department of Chemistry, College of Science, Qassim University, Ar Rass 51921, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 15-02-2025

Accepted: 22-03-2025

Published: 29-03-2025

Citation: Al-Qadri FA, Al-Yusufy FAS, Al-Qahtan J, Al-Hilali A, Bawazir A, Al-Sayari SS, Al-Sayari SS, Al-Nahdi M, Alkorbi B (2025) Banana Peel and Potato as a Biodegradable Plastic. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 18(10): 796-802. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v18i10.306>

* **Corresponding author.**

fatimaalqadri@gmail.com

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2025 Al-Qadri et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.indjst.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Abstract

Objectives: The research aims to produce bioplastic using starch, a polymer generated from natural plants that is abundantly available, affordable, biodegradable, and environmentally beneficial, such as potato and banana peel waste. **Methods:** Glycerol, acetic acid, and sodium hydroxide were added to banana peels and potato pastes in two separate beakers to produce bioplastic. After thoroughly mixing and having cured, they were removed from the petri dish, and the biodegradable plastic was subjected to a series of tests to determine the physical properties, including biodegradability, solubility, swelling, moisture content, and electron-scanning microscopy. **Findings:** In terms of biodegradability, potato plastic is more biodegradable and degrades faster, with an average weight loss of 86%, than banana peel biodegradable plastic, which lost just 66.1% of its weight. The results of the solubility test of synthesized bioplastic from banana peel and potato starch revealed that it was partially soluble in water and nitric acid and insoluble in ethanol. The results of the swelling test for both bioplastics synthesized showed that there was not much change when soaked in chloroform. A slight increase in weight was observed when bioplastic soaked in water. According to the moisture test results, the average percentage of weight loss for potato bioplastic was 29.51%, while the average percentage of weight loss for bananas was 17.38%. **Novelty:** As a result, the synthesized bioplastic material possesses significant qualities such as little or no swelling and insolubility in water, making it commercially viable, and renewable resources (banana and potato) will be the best raw materials for bioplastics synthesis.

Keywords: Bioplastics; Glycerol; Banana peel; Potato; Soil

1 Introduction

Plastics are extensively used for packaging due to their specific qualities such as lightweight, cost-effectiveness, environmental inertness, non-permeability, durability,

stability, and availability. These qualities cause plastics to remain in the environment for a long period and collect as solid trash⁽¹⁾. Plastics have become one of the most serious environmental issues because they decompose slowly and can remain in the environment for hundreds or thousands of years⁽²⁾. Microorganisms spontaneously decompose bioplastics into carbon dioxide and water, making them biodegradable. Bio-based polymers are made from renewable materials like cellulose, starch, and protein. Currently, bioplastics account for approximately 50% of the bioplastics used commercially and are manufactured from starch⁽³⁾. Bioplastics are plastics made from renewable biomass sources such as vegetable fats and oils, corn starch, straw, wood chips, food waste, agricultural byproducts, and recycled plastic bottles and other containers through the use of microbes. Bioplastic is translucent, flexible, robust, an excellent barrier, and heat-resistant. Starch dissolves quickly in water, which is the primary plasticizer for starch. Starch's brittleness and low mechanical characteristics make it difficult to turn into plastic, resulting in poor film-forming capacity. These issues can be solved through plasticization and blending with other polymers such as cellulose, proteins, and lipids⁽⁴⁾. All of these properties of starch for bioplastics apply to the potato and banana peel starch used in this study, which meets the requirements for bioplastics, so the objective of this research is to develop an environmentally friendly, simple biodegradable plastic in soil to replace synthetic plastic using potato and banana peel. Glycerol was used as a plasticizer. Biodegradability, solubility, moistness, swelling tests and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis. Were all conducted under safe settings to justify the production of bioplastic.

2 Methodology

2.1 Materials and Methods

Potato and Banana were purchased from a local market in Sharoura city – Saudi Najran Arabia. Plasticizer (glycerol), sodium hydroxide, Nitric acid, distilled water HCl (Hydrochloric acid), NaOH (sodium Hydroxide), acetic acid, Distilled water, ethanol, chloroform. All chemicals are acquired from Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2 Preparing Starch from Potato and banana peel

Potatoes have been washed of dust and skin. then were placed in a saucepan and covered with warm water for many hours. The potatoes were then filtered using a cloth strainer, and the cloth was wrung forcefully to extract as much water as possible. This technique was done multiple times until the water was mostly clear. The extracted water will then be settled for around 25 minutes, allowing the potato starch to settle to the bottom of the pot. Figure 1 shows the starch was permitted to dry firmly. The dried starch was then powdered using a grinder for both banana⁽⁵⁾. Figure 2 show the starch produced from banana; banana peels were boiled in water for approximately 60 minutes. The water was decanted from the beaker, and the peels were allowed to dry on filter paper for around 30 minutes. After incubation, the peels were thoroughly dried and placed in the mortar, where they were squished with a hand blender until a homogenous paste was created.

Fig 1. Bioplastics with the composition of potato

Fig 2. Bioplastics with the composition of banana peel

2.3 Bioplastic Production from Banana peel and potato Paste

Bioplastics were produced from potato and banana peel paste; the two pastes were placed separately into two beakers, and 5 ml of acetic acid (0.1N) was added to 15 grams of each sample. The samples were then blended with a glass rod. After that, 10 ml of glycerol was added to each beaker, and the samples were mixed again separately. After that, a solution of sodium hydroxide (0.1N) was added to raise the pH to 7.3 in each mixture, and then the samples were poured into two separate petri dishes. The bioplastic was then dried at room temperature for about 48 hours. The bioplastic became apparent after the petri dish cooled, and the layer was scraped away and stored for further analysis⁽⁶⁾.

2.4 Swelling test

A swelling study is generally conducted to check whether developed bioplastic retains the original properties when it was formed during the preparations. A preweighed piece of sample was prepared and taken in the test tube to check the protuberance and other morphological changes. It was carried out in various solvents, such as water and chloroform. The bioplastic samples were kept in the solvents for about 2 hours, and the results were recorded accordingly.

2.5 Biodegradability

Bioplastic materials weighing 2.11 grams of banana and potato were buried 5 cm deep in two soil-filled beakers. Water was sprayed on the soil to promote bacterial enzymatic activity. The bioplastic sample's weight change was measured over a period of about 8 days. Every two days for eight days, the rate of degradation is estimated using the observed changes and the period required for significant degradation. The bioplastic's final mass after degradation was determined when its weight decreased⁽⁷⁾. The biodegradability bioplastics and results were calculated using the following equation:

$$WL(\%) = \frac{W_0 - W_t}{W_0}$$

W_0 and W are the initial and final weight of bioplastic samples, respectively. Also, WL refers to the Weight Loss

2.6 Solubility test

The solubility test was designed to confirm the durability of these biodegradable bioplastics⁽⁸⁾. The samples were sliced into 10x10 cm and placed into test tubes containing various solvents, including nitric acid, distilled water, and ethyl alcohol. A bioplastic substance was examined for its solubility. The solvents were selected in such a way that the activity of material with parameters such as high acidic solvent, polar solvent, non-polar solvent, and weak acid was established.

$$solubility\% = \frac{W_0 - W_1}{W_0 - W_2} \times 100$$

2.7 Determining the moisture content

A crucible that had been previously dried and weighed was filled with two grams of fresh bioplastic. The materials were dried using oven combustion at 35°C until their weight remained constant. The samples were taken out of the oven, cooled in a desiccator for an hour, and then weighed again. After calculating the moisture content using the following equation as a percentage of the original sample's weight loss.

$$moisture = \frac{w_2 - w_1}{W_1} \times 100$$

Where W_1 = initial weight of bioplastic, W_2 is the weight of final weight of bioplastic.

2.8 SEM Analysis

The procedures were carried out based on ASTM E1508-12a Standard Guide for Quantitative Analysis by Energy-Dispersive Spectroscopy. For the microanalysis and failure analysis of solid inorganic materials, SEM analysis is very useful. A concentrated beam of high-energy electrons is used in SEM to generate a variety of signals at the specimen's surface. Data are typically collected over a predetermined portion of the sample's surface in SEM analyses. This method is especially useful for determining crystalline structure, crystal orientations, and chemical compositions in a qualitative or semi-quantitative manner⁽⁹⁾.

3 Results and Discussion

The findings of this study show that bioplastics made from banana peels and potatoes are a source of starch, the primary material in bioplastics, and are sustainable, safe, ecologically benign, and renewable. Furthermore, bioplastics derived from banana peels and potatoes are easily biodegradable in soil, unlike synthetic plastic, which is nonbiodegradable and one of the world's major pollutants. The percentage biodegradability was 86% for potato and 66 for Banana. The bioplastics generated in this study were made from natural and safe components, and the approach utilized was more successful than previous procedures that used chemical and non-eco-friendly materials. Similar results were recorded for the biofilm of potato starch. Solubility is an important factor in selecting a sustainable biomaterial for bioplastic since a material that is soluble in water and other solvents cannot be classified as bioplastic. The solubility test results revealed that the material is insoluble in water and other organic solvents, making bioplastic production more efficient and cost-effective.⁽⁸⁾

3.1 SEM Analysis

Figure 3 (a, b) shows the characteristics of the surface morphology of the biodegradable plastic based on potato and banana peels, as determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis. The micrographs essentially show that the bioplastic is evenly spaced throughout the thermoplastic starch matrix. The surfaces of the composites are comparatively smooth and have few flaws⁽¹⁰⁾. This demonstrates that the bioplastic made of banana peel extract is compatible with achieving good interaction in the composites and that it actually causes blemishes that may have been caused by uneven stirring.

Fig 3. Scanning electron micrograph of a) Banana peel b) potato

3.2 Biodegradable test for each Banana peel and Potato

The aim of the biodegradable test is to measure how well bioplastics break down when they are broken down by microorganisms in the soil⁽¹¹⁾. In this study, as shown in Figure 4 (a, b), bioplastics were subjected to a biodegradable test for 8 days, with results recorded in Table 1, with the mass before and after the test being compared. In light of the biodegradable test's findings, the bioplastic samples that are listed in Table 1 show mass loss between the starting and final masses. Both bioplastics produced from banana and potato samples had degraded with interval time. Their biodegradability reduces mass over time; this is due to the combination of starch and the OH groups in glycerol helping to start hydrolysis reactions so that they can absorb water from the soil, which results in the starch-based polymer being broken down into tiny fragments until the bioplastic is completely broken down in the ground. The percentage biodegradability was 86% for potato and 66% for Banana. Our findings suggest that bioplastic films made from potato and banana peel starch can be a sustainable alternative to synthetic plastics.

3.3 Percentage biodegradation

Percentage biodegradation was calculated for both samples produced from banana and potato. Table 1 and Figure 5 a and b, which display the percentage degradation with interval time, were used to list the results. The degradation increases with the number of days.

Fig 4. Biodegradation with days a) Banana b) Potato

Fig 5. Percentage Bio degradation with days a) Banana b) Potato

Table 1. Biodegradability test result for 8 days

Banana's peel weight in gm		Potato weight in gm		Days	Weight in gm (initial weight)
Weight %	Final Wt ₁	Weight %	Final Wt ₁		
0	0	0	2.11	0	2.11
33	1.4	43	1.7	2	2.11
52.1	2	57	1.21	4	2.11
62	0.8	76	1.61	6	2.11
66	0.7	86	1.11	8	2.11

3.4 Solubility Test

The results of the solubility test of bioplastics are presented in Table 2. The results of the study revealed that the material is more qualified to be a bioplastic because it was partially soluble in water. Additionally, it was insoluble in the non-polar solvent ethyl alcohol and partially soluble in the highly acidic solvent nitric acid. The bioplastic is insoluble in water and other organic solvents, according to the solubility test results, which increases the efficiency of producing bioplastic at a low cost⁽¹²⁾.

3.5 Swelling Test

hows the results of the swelling tests on bioplastics. The study's findings revealed that the sample does not change significantly when soaked in chloroform but does slightly increase in weight when kept in a water medium, making it more desirable as a bioplastic material that will aid in product stabilization and development⁽¹³⁾.

Table 2. Solubility Test of synthesized bioplastics

Sample no	Solvents	Potato			Banana		
		Solubility Test			Solubility Test		
		Insoluble	Partially	Completely	Insoluble	Partially	Completely
1	Water	-	+	-	-	+	-
2	Ethyl alcohol	+	-	-	+	-	-
3	Nitric acid	-	+	-	-	+	-

+ = Positive; - = Negative

Table 3. Swelling Test of synthesized bioplastics

Solvent	Potato			Banana		
	Initial Weight	Final Weight	Difference	Initial Weight	Final Weight	Difference
Water	2.88	3.73	0.85	16.7	19.6	.29
Chloroform	0.6	0.63	0.03	2.7	4.1	1.4

3.6 Moisture content

As demonstrated in Table 4, the weight decreased, so the result was fairly good and satisfactory; the results indicate that the produced bioplastic is moisture-resistant because it will be intended to replace synthetic plastic.

Table 4. Moisture content of synthesized bioplastics

Sample	Initial Weight (g)	Final Weight(g)	Moisture %
Banana	3.73	2.88	29.51
Potato	16.7	19.6	17.36

Table 5. Comparison with previous studies % weight loss Test of synthesized bioplastics in the soil

Sample	% weight Loss	References
Banana peels	65.10%	(14)
Potato	71%	(15)
Banana peels	66%	Present study
Potato	86%	Present study

4 Conclusion

This study made an effort to synthesize bioplastics from natural sources and characterize these sorts of natural bioplastic materials. This study employed glycerol, and sodium hydroxide in a mixture with banana peels and potato pastes in two separate beakers to create bioplastic. After mixing and drying, the bioplastic was pulled from the petri dish. Several experiments were carried out to determine the physical qualities, including biodegradability, solubility, swelling, moisture content, and electron-scanning microscopy. The outcome of degradation for both bioplastics made by potatoes and bananas was 66% and 86%, respectively, which was reasonable and acceptable; the result of the solubility for both bioplastics was insoluble in ethyl alcohol and partially soluble in water and nitric acid; the result of swelling was not much change when soaked in chloroform. A slight increase in weight was observed when bioplastic was soaked in water. According to the moisture test results, the average percentage of weight loss for potato bioplastic was 29.51%, while the average percentage of weight loss for bananas was 17.38%.

Novelty: As a result, the synthesized bioplastic material possesses significant qualities such as little or no engorgement and insolubility in water, making it commercially viable, and renewable resources (banana and potato) will be the best raw materials for bioplastics synthesis.

Future prospects: The production of biobased plastics from agro-based industrial residues, particularly banana-peel potato, has made significant progress, despite the use of sugar or starch in previous attempts. Bio-polyester-based polymers can be used as feedstock for numerous purposes. This would increase the value proposition for agro-industries by utilizing fruit waste and minimizing the need for food feedstock for biobased plastic manufacture. Nonetheless, fresh bioresources are

constantly sought for the production of novel biobased polymers. The recent research can open up a new route or place for the development of novel biobased polymers. Food packaging materials have a shorter shelf life and can be biodegraded within 3 months, making them ideal for industrial packaging applications. Approximately 30% of all food produced is wasted, with the majority occurring in supermarkets during peak sales periods. Using biodegradable/biobased plastics to extend the shelf life of consumable products can effectively reduce food waste. Using biobased materials can reduce food waste by 10%, outweighing the additional acreage required for dumping during the recycling process. Using these processes to convert agricultural waste to biobased polymers has significant economic possibilities in this century.

Recommendation for the researchers: To conduct additional research in order to develop the project of bioplastic manufacture from waste vegetables and fruits, as well as to discover some other natural additives that will give our plastic greater qualities.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank the Chemistry Department, Sharurah Science and Art Faculty, Najran University, laboratory for the facilities to achieve this work.

References

- 1) Arkan EB, Bilgen HD. Production of bioplastic from potato peel waste and investigation of its biodegradability. *International Advanced Researches and Engineering Journal*. 2019;3(2):93–97. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.35860/iarej.420633>.
- 2) Chandarana J, Chandra S. Production of Bioplastics from banana peels. *International Journal of Scientific Research & Engineering Trends*. 2021;7(1):131–133. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/star.202400178>.
- 3) Karne HU, Gaydhane P, Gohokar V, Deshpande K, Dunung P, Bendkule G. Synthesis of biodegradable material from banana peel. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. 2023. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2023.05.157>.
- 4) Olagundoye AA, Morayo AO. Characterization of Potato Peel Starch-based Bioplastic Reinforced with Banana Pseudostem Cellulose for Packaging Applications. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*. 2022;7(4):1360–1371. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6571367>.
- 5) Dutta D, Sit N. Preparation and characterization of potato starch-based composite films reinforced by modified banana fibers and its application in packaging of grapes. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. 2024;254(Part 2):127791. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.127791>.
- 6) Jayasinghe CVL, Rajapakse HUKDZ, Kithmini NKS, Senevirathne SS, Wanigasinghe HG, Kulathunga KMPM. Valorization of Banana Waste and Its Applications in Food Packaging. In: *Agro-Wastes for Packaging Applications*. CRC Press. 2024;p. 105. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003453277>.
- 7) Rajesh Y, Gautam N, Saloni P, Deore V, Shivde P, Dabhade G. Agricultural resources in focus: Eco-friendly bioplastic synthesis from corn starch. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. 2024;111:182–187. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2024.01.025>.
- 8) Noorjahan CM, Banu SN, Subhashree V. Bioplastic Synthesis Using Banana Peels And Its Characterization. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*. 2022;13(Special Issue7):2855–2863. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.47750/pnr.2022.13.S07.380>.
- 9) Yang J, Ching YC, Chuah CH, Hai ND, Singh R, Nor ARM. Preparation and characterization of starch-based bioplastic composites with treated oil palm empty fruit bunch fibers and citric acid. *Cellulose*. 2021;28:4191–4210. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-021-03816-8>.
- 10) Nazar M, Hasan M, Wirjosentono B, Gani BA. Fabrication and characterization of bio-nanocomposite from sweet potato starch and Moringa oleifera leaf extract loaded with carbon quantum dots from Coffea arabica grounds. *Results in Engineering*. 2024;23:1–12. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.102448>.
- 11) Maura CS, Athariq M, and RM. Utilization of Plantain Peel (*Musa sapientum*) and Sweet Potato Starch (*Ipomea batatas*) Waste in Combination with Glycerol Addition to Produce Biodegradable Plastic. *Chemistry and Materials*. 2024;3(2):50–55. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.102448>.
- 12) Abera WG, Kasirajan R, Majamo SL. Synthesis and characterization of bioplastic film from banana (*Musa Cavendish* species) peel starch blending with banana pseudo-stem cellulosic fiber. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*. 2023;14:20419–20440. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-023-04207-8>.
- 13) Maitlo G, Ali I, Maitlo HA, Ali S, Unar IN, Ahmad MB, et al. Plastic Waste Recycling, Applications, and Future Prospects for a Sustainable Environment. *Sustainability*. 2022;14(8):1–27. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141811637>.
- 14) Beevi KR, Fathima ARS, Fathima AIT, Thameemunisa N, Noorjahan CM, Deepika T. Bioplastic synthesis using banana peels and potato starch and characterization. *International journal of scientific & technology research*. 2020;9(1):1809–1814. Available from: <https://www.ijstr.org/final-print/jan2020/Bioplastic-Synthesis-Using-Banana-Peels-And-Potato-Starch-And-Characterization.pdf>.
- 15) Vijayalaksmi M, Kiran VG, Varsha AK, Govindaraj V, Anisha M, Vigneshwari N, et al. Synthesis and characterization of banana peel starch-based bioplastic for intravenous tubes preparation. *Materials Today Communications*. 2022;33:104464. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2022.104464>.